

Feedback on the JEFF-4.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1 nuclear data evaluations for Criticality Safety and Burnup applications

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ABSTRACT

The latest nuclear data evaluations from the US and Europe, namely ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JEFF-4.0, have recently been released, reflecting years of evaluation and validation efforts by both communities. These libraries have undergone rigorous testing, mainly through integral experiments (criticality benchmark), but also for burnup related applications aiming to address the reactivity bias observed in depletion calculations, particularly with the JEFF-3.3 library. The presented work focuses on the testing of these recent nuclear data libraries for criticality safety and burnup calculations. Monte Carlo simulations were conducted using the MORET 6 code on selected ICSBEP benchmark cases to evaluate the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) using ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JEFF-4.0, in comparison to the benchmark value. In parallel, depletion calculations were performed with the VESTA 2.2 code on a UO₂ pincell benchmark, enabling a comparative analysis between the different libraries.

Keywords. JEFF-4.0, ENDF/B-VIII.1, Monte-Carlo, benchmarking, depletion

1. INTRODUCTION

In the pursuit of ever-greater precision in nuclear data, evaluation and validation remain ongoing and iterative processes. As computational capabilities and modeling techniques continue to advance, the demand for reliable and high-fidelity nuclear data becomes increasingly critical across both research and industrial applications. Two new US and European nuclear data libraries, ENDF/B-VIII.1 [1] and JEFF-4.0 [2], have been recently released. Both are considered being at the forefront of the state of the art in the nuclear data community.

ENDF/B-VIII.1 builds upon the foundation laid by ENDF/B-VIII.0 [3], integrating updated evaluations for a wide range of isotopes — including actinides, light nuclei, and structural materials — based on recent experimental measurements and theoretical developments. The library incorporates the latest IAEA standards, refined thermal neutron scattering data, and enhanced photonuclear and charged-particle sub-libraries. Major updates were introduced with a particular emphasis on the re-evaluation of actinides including the key isotopes of uranium (²³⁵U, ²³⁸U) and plutonium (²³⁹Pu). Notably, ENDF/B-VIII.1 addresses limitations observed in previous versions, particularly in burnup applications, where reactivity biases were observed.

The JEFF-4.0 (Joint Evaluated Fission and Fusion, version 4.0) nuclear data library, released in June 2025 by the OECD Nuclear Energy Agency, represents a major milestone in European nuclear data development. Building on the foundation of JEFF-3.3 [4], this new version incorporates eight years of collaborative work across European institutions and introduces substantial improvements in both evaluated data and application performance. Key updates include refined neutron-induced reaction data

for critical actinides such as ^{235}U , ^{238}U and ^{239}Pu , as well as updated thermal fission yields for ^{235}U , ^{238}U , ^{239}Pu and ^{241}Pu . The thermal scattering sub-library has been significantly expanded to cover 84 materials — elemental and compound forms — enhancing modeling accuracy for hydrogen in water among others. JEFF-4.0 also integrates new decay and activation data, a proton-induced reaction sub-library, and selected TENDL evaluations for charged-particle reactions. Designed as a general-purpose resource, JEFF-4.0 supports a wide range of applications, including criticality safety, reactor physics, fusion research and medical isotope production.

2. MONTE-CARLO SIMULATIONS

2.1. MORET 6 Monte-Carlo simulations

MORET 6 [5] is the latest version of the MORET Monte Carlo neutron transport code developed by the French Nuclear Safety and Radioprotection Authority (ASNR), designed for high-fidelity criticality safety analyses applications. It supports three-dimensional geometry modeling with a flexible combinatorial geometry system and includes advanced variance reduction techniques to optimize simulation efficiency. The code is capable of handling complex reactor configurations and fuel cycle scenarios, and it offers detailed treatment of neutron interactions using continuous-energy cross sections processed in ACE format. The continuous energy version of the MORET code has been validated [6], using various JEFF and ENDF/B nuclear data libraries, on a suite of more than 2000 criticality benchmarks issued from the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) Handbook [7] and French proprietary experiments, allowing thus covering the main applications encountered in criticality safety. All nuclear data libraries are processed at ASNR into ACE format using the GAIA-NJOY processing system [8], which relies on NJOY [9].

2.2. VESTA 2.2 depletion Monte-Carlo simulations

VESTA [10] is a computational tool developed by ASNR that couples a Monte-Carlo neutron transport solver with a depletion module. The code alternates between steady-state Monte Carlo transport calculations and depletion steps, using flux and reaction rate data from the transport phase to solve the Bateman equations and track the evolution of isotopic concentrations. VESTA supports depletion simulations across various geometrical scales, including detailed isotopic composition calculations at the pin cell level during irradiation. The latest version, VESTA 2.2 [10], offers compatibility with both the MCNP(X/6) [11] and MORET 5 Monte Carlo transport codes, and supports multiple depletion modules: ORIGEN 2.2, PHOENIX, and FISPACT. The transport calculations presented below were performed with MCNP6.1 and the material evolution is computed using the PHOENIX module, which solves the Bateman equations through a Runge-Kutta integration scheme.

VESTA 2.2 has undergone extensive experimental validation [12], including isotopic inventory predictions for 90 nuclides across 53 radiochemical samples and 52 decay heat measurements. This full validation was performed using several nuclear data libraries: JEFF-3.1, JEFF-3.2, ENDF/B-VII.0, and ENDF/B-VII.1. The benchmark cases span a wide range of reactor types (PWR, BWR, VVER) and fuel compositions (UOX, MOX), with and without burnable absorbers. Validation was carried out using both MCNPX/6 and MORET 5 for transport, and PHOENIX for depletion. Most benchmark cases used in the validation campaign are drawn from the NEA's Spent Fuel Isotopic Composition Database (SFCOMPO). As with the libraries for MORET 6, all nuclear data libraries for VESTA are processed at ASNR into PENDF and ACE format at various temperatures using the GAIA-NJOY processing system [8].

3. CRITICALITY SAFETY RESULTS USING ICSBEP BENCHMARKS

3.1.1. Benchmark selection

The objective of this benchmark selection process is to identify a set of cases that exhibit k_{eff} sensitivity to the cross sections of ^{235}U , ^{238}U , and ^{239}Pu , thereby enabling validation of their nuclear data. To this end, the open-source CALINS tool [13], developed at ASNR, was used to analyze two sensitivity databases: one derived from DICE-2021 [14], and another generated using MORET 6 and the JEFF-3.3 nuclear data library at ASNR. The methodology followed consists of three main steps:

- **Merging of sensitivity databases:** The datasets from MORET6 and DICE-2021 were combined by incorporating cases exclusive to MORET 6 into the DICE-2021 base to extract the sensitivities;
- **Initial filtering:** Only the benchmarks present in the MORET 6 validation database were used. Benchmarks lacking experimental uncertainty data, or those with uncertainties exceeding 500 pcm (1σ), were excluded;
- **Sensitivity analysis:** The filtered database was examined to identify cases sensitive to the total cross section (MT1) of each isotope within one of the following three energy domains:
 - *Thermal.* [1e-5 eV ; 0.625 eV];
 - *Epithermal.* [0.625 eV ; 100 keV];
 - *Fast.* [100 keV ; 20 MeV].

A benchmark is considered sensitive if the k_{eff} exhibits an integral sensitivity greater than 0.5% within the considered energy range. This relatively permissive threshold serves to exclude only those cases where the influence of the cross section can be deemed negligible.

The final selection consisted in identifying the five most sensitive benchmarks identified from the filtered database for each ISOTOPE – REACTION – ENERGY REGION combination. Additional selection criteria were applied to further refine the benchmark set. Benchmarks involving ^{233}U fuel were systematically excluded to maximize sensitivity to ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu fissile isotopes. Furthermore, to minimize redundancy and reduce the impact of inter-series correlations, only one benchmark per experimental series was retained. This approach ensures a more diverse and representative dataset while avoiding potential biases introduced by repeated configurations. Duplicate cases were also removed to streamline the benchmark base. *Table I* summarizes the final selection of the five most sensitive benchmarks identified for each isotope–energy region combination, based on the analysis of total cross section sensitivity.

Table I. Benchmark selection using most sensitive k_{eff} to total cross-section of ^{235}U , ^{238}U and ^{239}Pu in each energy region.

	Thermal	Epithermal	Fast
U235	LEU-SOL-THERM-003-007, LEU-COMP-THERM-033-044, IEU-SOL-THERM-002-004, LEU-SOL-THERM-003-004, LEU-SOL-THERM-025-001	HEU-COMP-INTER-004-001, HEU-MET-FAST-067-001, HEU-MET-FAST-070-003, HEU-MET-INTER-006-002, IEU-MET-FAST-010-001	HEU-MET-FAST-018-001, HEU-MET-FAST-001-001, HEU-MET-FAST-065-001, HEU-MET-FAST-015-001, HEU-MET-FAST-008-001

U238	LEU-MET-THERM-006-030, LEU-COMP-THERM-033-001, LEU-COMP-THERM-003-022, LEU-COMP-THERM-064-005, LEU-COMP-THERM-017-021	LEU-COMP-THERM-033-047, LEU-COMP-THERM-049-004, LEU-COMP-THERM-063-011, LEU-COMP-THERM-045-015, LEU-COMP-THERM-072-009	IEU-MET-FAST-008-001, HEU-MET-FAST-032-002, PU-MET-FAST-020-001, PU-MET-FAST-006-001, HEU-MET-FAST-002-001
Pu239	PU-SOL-THERM-012-002, PU-SOL-THERM-034-006, MIX-SOL-THERM-003-010, MIX-SOL-THERM-007-007, PU-SOL-THERM-030-002	MIX-COMP-FAST-001-001, MIX-COMP-FAST-006-001, MIX-COMP-FAST-005-001, MIX-MET-INTER-004-001, MIX-MET-INTER-003-001	PU-MET-FAST-022-001, PU-MET-FAST-001-001, PU-MET-FAST-025-001, PU-MET-FAST-035-001, PU-MET-FAST-040-001

3.1.2. Results

Figure 1 shows the k_{eff} C-C (ENDF/B-VIII.1 - JEFF-4.0), C-E and cumulative χ^2/N values obtained with MORET 6 for the 5 benchmarks the more sensitive to the three isotopes in each energy domain. In the left part of *Figure 1*, σ_{ref} denotes the benchmark uncertainty (from DICE), σ_{calc} the uncertainty from the MORET 6 and σ_{cumul} the cumulative uncertainty associated with C-C values, defined as: $\sigma_{cumul} = \sqrt{\sigma_{calc,1}^2 + \sigma_{calc,2}^2}$.

Within each domain, the benchmarks are ordered by the average lethargy causing fission (EALF) value. While most cases show minimal differences between evaluations, a large impact is observed for the benchmarks sensitive to the epithermal domain of ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu , as well as to the thermal domain of ^{239}Pu total cross-sections.

The top five benchmarks sensitive to the epithermal domain of ^{235}U — HCI-004-001 (HECTOR), HMI-006-002 (ZEUS-2), HMF-070-003, HMF-067-001 and IMF-010-001 — exhibit EALF values varying from 140 eV to 400 keV. For HECTOR, with the smallest EALF, ENDF/B-VIII.1 significantly overestimates the k_{eff} by more than 500 pcm compared to JEFF-4.0. The same applies to HMF-070-003 and HMF-067-001 with EALF values of 60 keV and 130 keV respectively. Because the ENDF/B-VIII.1 results tend to overestimate the benchmark k_{eff} , the JEFF-4.0 results are in better agreement with the benchmark value. It is especially the case for HECTOR, where the large deviation observed for ENDF/B-VIII.1 is significantly reduced using JEFF-4.0 and falls back within the $3\sigma_{cumul}$. For ZEUS-2 and IMF-010-001, which show an EALF of 10 keV and 400 keV respectively, both libraries yield k_{eff} values in perfect agreement with each other and with the benchmark value.

The top five benchmarks sensitive to the thermal domain of ^{239}Pu — PST-012-002, MST-003-010, PST-030-002, MST-007-007 and PST-034-006— exhibit different results, as a function of their EALF values varying from $4.8\text{e-}2$ eV to 0.28 eV. The three first ones, having EALF value below $5.3\text{e-}2$ eV, show a significant overestimation of more than 350 pcm with ENDF/B-VIII.1 relative to JEFF-4.0, which provides slightly better agreement with experiment. MST-007-007, characterized by an EALF of 0.19 eV, presents a perfect agreement between the two libraries, although both strongly underestimate the benchmark value by over 800 pcm. Lastly, PST-034-006, with an EALF of 0.28 eV, shows a moderate underestimation of around 200 pcm with ENDF/B-VIII.1 compared to JEFF-4.0.

Finally, the top five benchmarks sensitive to the epithermal domain of ^{239}Pu , being MMI-003-001, MMI-004-001, MCF-001-001, MCF-006-001 and MCF-005-001, have EALF values varying from 30 keV to 190 keV. For all of them, a strong underestimation of more than 500 pcm is observed in ENDF/B-VIII.1 compared to JEFF-4.0. Because the JEFF-4.0 results tend to overestimate the benchmark k_{eff} , the ENDF/B-VIII.1 results are in fact in better agreement with the benchmark value and falls back within the $3\sigma_{cumul}$.

Regarding cumulative χ^2/N values, JEFF-4.0 shows a slightly better overall performance than ENDF/B-VIII.1 for the selected benchmarks, mainly due to a more accurate prediction of k_{eff} for HECTOR.

Figure 1. k_{eff} C-E (top) and C-C (bottom) obtained with MORET 6 (left side) and cumulative χ^2/N (right side) for the benchmarks sensitive to ^{235}U (left), ^{238}U (middle), and ^{239}Pu (right) in each energy domain

Sensitivity profiles and reaction rates were analyzed for each benchmark and each isotope. The most likely hypothesis to explain these results lies in the differences between the ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu fission cross-sections in the two nuclear data libraries, as these isotopes were identified as main impact contributors. As presented in Figure 2, the ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu fission cross-sections differ between the two libraries, especially in the Unresolved Resonance Region (URR). Fluctuations have been embedded into the ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu ENDF/B-VIII.1 fission cross-sections. These fluctuations, derived from experimental fission data, appear in the URR up to ~ 100 keV for ^{235}U and up to ~ 20 keV for ^{239}Pu , while JEFF-4.0 uses typical smooth cross-section in the URR above 2.25 keV and 4.5 keV respectively. These differences, particularly at energies around the keV to several tens of keV, corresponding to the EALF values of the benchmarks discussed above, are a highly plausible explanation for the discrepancies observed in these cases.

Figure 2. ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu fission cross-sections (top), and ratio ENDF/B-VIII.1/JEFF-4.0 (bottom)

4. BURNUP APPLICATIONS

4.1.1. Benchmark case

The exercise I-1b of the OECD LWR UAM benchmark [15] aims to evaluate criticality parameters and nuclide concentrations along with their associated uncertainties in a simplified pin cell model. The test case involves a representative fuel rod from the TMI-1 PWR, based on a 15×15 assembly design. The geometry, irradiation history, and material specifications used in the VESTA simulation are detailed in *Figure 3* and *Table II*. The fuel pin was modeled in an infinite medium using VESTA 2.2 in conjunction with the MORET 5 Monte-Carlo code and subjected to an irradiation cycle reaching approximately 61 GWd/t of burnup. This irradiation history was discretized into 61 steps, each corresponding to a burnup increment of 1 GWd/t, following the methodology described in [15]. The moderator and cladding temperatures were set to 600 K, while the fuel temperature was maintained at 900 K.

Table II. Overview of the UAM pin cell characteristics.

Figure 3. UAM pin cell configuration

Type	PWR	Unit
Fuel type	UO2	
$^{235}\text{U}/\text{U}$	4.85	%
$\text{Pu} / \text{U} + \text{Pu}$	-	%
Gd203 / oxide	-	%
Active fuel length	357.12	cm
Fuel density	10.283	$\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$
Estimated burn up	61.3	GWd/t
Specific power	33.58	MW/t
Irradiation time	1825	days
Pin pitch	1.44	cm
Fuel pellet diameter	0.939	cm
Cladding material	Zr-4	
Moderator type	H2O (no boron)	

4.1.2. Results

The k_{∞} values were extracted from different ENDF/B and JEFF libraries as a function of irradiation time. *Figure 4* shows the k_{∞} discrepancies results obtained with VESTA 2.2 for ENDF/B-VIII.1, ENDF/B-VIII.0, ENDF/B-VII.1, JEFF-4.0 and JEFF-3.3 nuclear data libraries, with respect to JEFF-3.1.1, for the UAM pin cell benchmark. The statistical errors are of 40 pcm in 1σ on the VESTA calculations.

Figure 4. Δk_{∞} with respect to JEFF-3.1.1

The Δk_{∞} values with respect to JEFF-3.1.1 stay more or less flat with burnup for most libraries, with the exception of JEFF-3.3. As already discussed in different papers [12][16], the JEFF-3.3 results show a strong negative trend with burnup, which ends with an underestimation of ~ 900 pcm at the end of irradiation, with respect to the JEFF-3.1.1 results. JEFF-3.3 ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu evaluations mainly explain this result, as well as their fission yields. For ENDF/B-VIII.1 and ENDF/B-VIII.0, a noticeable underestimation at beginning of cycle of 300 pcm and 400 pcm respectively is observed with respect to JEFF-3.1.1. A slight positive trend is also observed for ENDF/B-VIII.1, with an overestimation of around 200 pcm at end of irradiation.

It is worth noting the very good agreement between the k_{∞} values obtained with JEFF-4.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1 beyond 15 GWd/t. Despite the discrepancies previously observed in the ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu cross-sections, and the results shown above on the ICSBEP benchmarks, these differences do not appear to impact the results with burnup.

Last but not least, unlike JEFF-3.3, the JEFF-4.0 library no longer shows any negative trend and is now overestimating JEFF-3.1.1 by around 200 pcm at end of cycle. Extensive work has been carried out to address the negative trend observed in JEFF-3.3, particularly concerning ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu cross-sections and their respective fission yields, which have been fully re-evaluated in JEFF-4.0. The results presented here are the outcome of a multi-year effort involving continuous evaluation and benchmarking across several beta releases of JEFF-4.0, ultimately leading to this result.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Recently released US and European nuclear data libraries, namely ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JEFF-4.0 libraries, as well as older ones, were used for benchmarking, both using ICSBEP cases and a burnup pincell benchmark case. Monte-Carlo calculations using MORET 6 and VESTA 2.2 were performed. JEFF-4.0 no longer exhibits the negative trend previously observed in JEFF-3.3 and now shows a slight overestimation compared to JEFF-3.1.1 at end of irradiation. This improvement stems essentially from substantial revisions to the ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu cross-sections and their associated fission yields, which were re-assessed in JEFF-4.0. In parallel, the criticality safety results obtained for a selected set of benchmarks — particularly those very sensitive to ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu — demonstrate very good performance, although discrepancies between ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JEFF-4.0 are observed, particularly in the epithermal domain.

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